

How accurate are Scopus publication counts of researchers? A survey-bibliometric comparison for Germany

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The number of researchers' publications is a widely used proxy measure for scientific output, individual achievement, and performance. Despite well-known criticism from the bibliometric community, the use of bibliometric databases as a basis for measuring publication output is widespread. At the same time, there are established survey instruments that also measure the publication output per researcher. We use survey-bibliometric matching with Scopus publication records to compare the alternative publication counts. A Scopus author ID match could be found for 70 % of the respondent researchers. The number of publications per researcher varies greatly between these data sources. The correlation is only 0.41 and the average individual Scopus coverage is 55 %. Importantly, we find a very high variance of individual-level coverage within disciplines, something that other approaches fail to detect.

1. Introduction

To ensure responsible application of bibliometric methods, it is crucial to understand how well a data source covers the relevant literature for a study. Coverage differs because data sources apply specific formal indexing criteria (e.g. Scopus does not index book reviews) and source inclusion criteria (formal conditions and expert judgments) which are meant to perform a selection for quality. A major deficit of current selection practice is that it remains unknown which publications and sources have been submitted and evaluated but were rejected, and for which reasons.

In principle, if the population of publications of interest is well-defined and a sample or census can be obtained, this can be matched against the database to obtain an estimate of the database's coverage of the literature. An informed decision to use a given data source can then be made based on whether the coverage is judged sufficient for the purposes of a planned study. In practice this is rarely done, either because the required data are difficult to assemble or the matching proves too labour-intensive. There is no consensus on what degree of coverage is sufficient to ensure reliable results. It also remains unknown if the publications of comparable quality of different researchers are represented to similar degrees.

Nevertheless, relatively complete publication data have been centrally collected and managed in several countries and used for national-level estimates of database coverage. A recent example is Kulczycki et al. (2018), who study peer-reviewed social science and humanities (SSH) publications from eight European nations. Numbers of publications are tallied by type and discipline and compared with publication counts in Web of Science (WoS) for those parameters. Estimates of WoS coverage for the countries' SSH publications from 2014 range from 15 % (Poland) to 51 % (Denmark).

Other approaches to estimating coverage are journal lists – Mongeon & Paul-Hus (2016), for example, compare Web of Science and Scopus journal lists to Ulrich's journal directory – or

internal reference coverage, such as in Moed (2005, Chapter 7). These have specific drawbacks, namely, journals are not publications and differ dramatically in size, while internal reference coverage is limited to the perspective of cited literature already covered in a database. The validity of these approaches has, to our knowledge, not been established.

As an alternative method, in this paper we use survey responses from researchers about numbers of their own publications as a reference for comparison to the numbers of their publications in Scopus. Thus, our method is similar to Kulczycki et al. (2018), as in both cases there is no one-to-one matching of publications, but a comparison of counts and allocation to publication types. Where Kulczycki et al. (2018) relied on current research information systems, we use self-reports from a survey. Furthermore, while their study compared the pattern on the level of disciplines and countries, we are able to compare the numbers on the level of individual researchers. This is a crucial methodological advance because it allows us to analyze distributions of individual researcher coverage values, which, unlike other methods, can inform us whether researchers' publications are included in a bibliometric database to comparable degrees or not.

2. Methods and data

The Scientists Survey (*Wissenschaftsbefragung*, WiBef)¹ is a cross-sectional trend survey of researchers at German universities and higher education institutions. The survey is conducted by the DZHW and includes questions about research and working conditions, attitudes to specific processes and developments in academia, as well as personal circumstances. Names and e-mail addresses of the target population were initially collected from publicly available websites of their respective institutions to generate the contact information dataset for the survey invitations. For detailed information see the methods documentation (Ambrasat, Heger, & Rucker, 2022b).

Consent was obtained from WiBef respondents to use their contact information to find matching records in third-party, e.g. bibliometric databases, without linking the survey data itself back to the contact data. Processed bibliometric data can be added to the survey data via an anonymity-securing procedure.

One novel element in our paper is a matching between WiBef survey respondents and Scopus author profiles. Scopus author profiles with author IDs group the publications imputed algorithmically as belonging to the same natural person. Our matching to these profiles is a mixed deterministic-probabilistic process. Definite matches are first made via exactly-matching email addresses. The probabilistic matches use a variety of common fields, such as given and family names and institutional affiliations. A random forest model, built on a training set of manually checked matches, is used to classify potential candidate matches. Manual checks suggest that a potential match exists for some 80 % of WiBef 2019 respondents. The combined matching finds just short of 90 % of these, and we estimate that around 1 % of the obtained matches are errors. The figures for cases, recall, and error rate of the matching procedure are shown in Table 1. The Scopus Author ID has been shown to generally provide good precision and acceptable recall, also for authors from Germany (Aman, 2018). However, not all publications of one real person are necessarily grouped under one ID. It is important to note that our matching procedure matched only the single most similar Author ID to the survey data without any consideration of the number of publications grouped under that ID. If no Scopus Author ID could be matched to a survey respondent

¹ <https://www.wb.dzhw.eu/en/index.html>

record, we treat that researcher as not included in Scopus and all Scopus publication counts are set as zero values.

Table 1: Cases, error and recall for the combined matching procedure

label	note	n	recall	error
EE	Exact Email Match	4362	0.628	0.000
P1	Probabilistic > 0.85	633	0.091	0.000
P2	Probabilistic > 0.65	1181	0.170	0.049
[All]	Combined	6176	0.889	0.009

The central question about the publications in the survey was as follows: "How many of the following publication formats can be found among your publications of the last 5 years? Please state the number or an estimate", with eight different publication types queried. Respondents answered by typing an integer number into the response field. We limit our analysis to the following four WiBef publication types and match them to the Scopus types given in parentheses: "Original articles in academic journals (incl. proceedings)" (Scopus: *Article, Article in Press, Conference Paper*), "Review articles in academic journals" (*Review, Short Survey*), "Monographs" (*Book*), "Book contributions (except in manuals)" (*Chapter*). We take these to be the most important formats for communicating new findings and synthesizing progress, disregarding some minor types such as *Editorials* and *Letters*.

Scopus-indexed publication records for the matched author IDs for the period 2014-2018 were retrieved and publication counts calculated by type and in total. Respondents reporting zero publications in the survey but with a matched Scopus record with some publications are not included in the calculations. Coverage percentages are calculated by dividing, for each respondent, the number of publications of one type in Scopus by the reported number of publications in the survey of the corresponding type, and subsequently averaging these individual author coverage estimates. We analyze the coverage distributions by plotting them and reporting percentages of researchers with more publications in WiBef than Scopus and vice versa. Correlation coefficients for the two publication counts are also reported.

3. Results

According to their survey responses, German researchers publish on average between 4 (humanities) and 15 (physics) research articles or conference papers in a 5-year span. While books are published infrequently, the international pattern (Kulczycki et al., 2018) is also observed for Germany in that the disciplines with most book publications are humanities, social and behavioral sciences and agricultural/veterinary sciences. These three disciplines also show the highest frequencies of book chapters. An overview of German researchers' publication statistics from this data can be found in Ambrasat & Heger (2020).

Table 2: Coverage of German authors' publications in Scopus (%)

science area	articles	reviews	books	book chapters	combined
agricultural and veterinary s.	69.0	42.6	8.3	28.9	62.6
biology	72.0	48.4	0.0	31.9	66.7
chemistry	70.1	40.6	2.1	44.0	64.2
earth sciences	81.0	37.7	3.1	32.4	74.9
engineering	80.8	18.0	1.6	27.4	65.3
humanities	17.5	10.7	5.8	7.2	11.9
mathematics	68.4	12.5	3.7	63.5	60.9
medicine	96.9	48.2	2.3	20.0	81.0
no field	70.5	17.8	6.9	18.7	60.4
physics	126.8	44.8	4.7	45.6	121.9
social and behavioral s.	43.1	22.7	6.4	12.8	34.0
total	65.6	31.2	5.0	19.1	55.3

Results for Scopus coverage are shown disaggregated for publication types and areas of science in Table 2. The average publication coverage of German researchers differs markedly between publication types and science areas. Articles/conference papers are covered most comprehensively of the examined types, albeit only moderately so in absolute terms, from between 17.5 % in the humanities to a perhaps surprising 126.8 % in physics, with an average coverage of 65.6 %. The seemingly impossible figure for physics is because respondents' claimed publication counts are on average lower than their publication counts found in Scopus. Coverage of reviews is more incomplete, with an average of 31.2 %. We have no ready explanation for this disparity, since presumably articles and reviews are mostly published in the same journals. Book chapter coverage is weaker at 19.1 %. Coverage of German authors' books in Scopus is negligible: 5 % on average. Coverage across all examined types together and considered by science area is between sixty and eighty percent for many disciplines. Exceptions are the humanities (11.9 %) and the social and behavioral sciences (34 %) and on the positive side, physics, with 121.9 %. The total average is 55.3 %. Our figures for the SSH are consistent with those of Kulczycki et al. (2018) for other European countries.

Table 3: Relations of WiBef to Scopus publication counts and correlations

science area	fewer in Scopus (%)	more in Scopus (%)	correlation
social and behavioral s.	89.9	5.9	0.55
physics	63.8	26.5	0.64
humanities	98.1	0.9	0.33
engineering	76.6	16.7	0.19
biology	71.8	17.8	0.68
mathematics	81.5	12.5	0.31
medicine	72.7	19.2	0.75
no field	86.2	10.0	0.58
chemistry	73.4	18.5	0.84
earth sciences	72.0	21.9	0.56
agricultural and veterinary s.	77.6	14.7	0.74
total	81.4	12.7	0.41

We have so far given coverage percentages as scalar point estimates. But in fact these are the arithmetic means of the distributions of publication coverages of individual researchers. Any particular researcher's value might be close to the average but it might also be much lower or

higher. In fact, the number of publications found in Scopus can exceed the one they reported in the survey. Calculating how many respondents' individual publication counts, all types combined, are greater, less, or equal in the survey versus Scopus, we arrive at the following results, see Table 3 for results by science areas. The number of self-reported publications is greater than that found in Scopus for 81 % of responding researchers; it is exactly equal for 6 %; and it is smaller in the survey than in Scopus for 13 % of respondents. Fig. 1 displays the histograms of the distributions of individual respondents' coverage values, showing that for many researchers the coverage is zero. The average is 55 % and the standard deviation is 130, which gives a 95 % confidence interval for the mean of [52, 58]. Nevertheless, the mean in this case tells us little about the typical coverage we might expect for any particular researcher as the variation around the mean is large.

Figure 1: Histogram of coverage distributions of German authors' publications in Scopus

One might argue that the Scopus data could still be useful if covered publications of a researcher form a statistical sample of all of their publications. Then relative comparisons would still produce consistent, if inaccurate, results. The Scopus source selection process is not intended to create random samples from a population, so this is unlikely. It can easily be tested by

calculating correlation coefficients. In a random sample, nearly the same *proportion* of each researcher's publications would be indexed. Therefore, the correlation between their total publication count and Scopus-indexed publication count should be very high. We find this is not so. The overall correlation for all four investigated publication types is 0.41. The values for each type are as follows: articles: 0.39, reviews: 0.4, books: 0.06, chapters: 0.16 (all $p < 0.05$). Table 3 gives the correlation coefficients by science areas.

4. Discussion

The survey-bibliometric comparison has shown that measurement of individual researchers' output in commercial databases such as Scopus diverges widely and falls short of the values reported by the researchers themselves. The commercial databases are thus wholly unsuited to individual-level analyses. The typical shares of researchers' publications which can be found in Scopus are low to moderate. Furthermore, the correlations between the two measurements are so low that a valid measurement of output cannot be assumed. This means that, even within one area of science, the Scopus publication counts of two compared researchers may be vastly underestimated for one researchers but vastly overestimated for the other one. Thus, our analyses raise doubts about the widespread use of publication count figures from bibliometric databases as a proxy for researchers' output in evaluation contexts and meta-research.

Open science practices

WiBef 2019/2020 data is available for scientific use at Ambrasat et al. (2022a). Scopus data is licenced proprietary data and cannot be made available.

Author contributions

AF: Conceptualisation, Data Curation, Software, Validation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Investigation

PD: Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization

JA: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Investigation

GF: Writing - Review & Editing, Data Curation, Investigation

CH: Writing - Review & Editing, Data Curation, Investigation

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests.

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